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DIGITALISATION OF TAX ADMINISTRATION HOW DOES IT WORK IN GREECE?

Abstract. *This article explores the process of digitalisation of tax administration in Greece and describes its main principles and mechanisms. The author considers the introduction of modern information technologies into the system of tax data collection and accounting, as well as the automation of tax administration processes. The study of the Greek experience allows to identify the key advantages and challenges faced in the implementation of digitalisation in this area.*

Keywords: *digitalisation, tax administration, Greece, information technology, automation.*

Μιχαηλόπουλος Ιωάννης

Υποψήφιος Διδάκτωρ Αριστοτελείου Πανεπιστημίου Θεσσαλονίκης,
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ΨΗΦΙΟΠΟΙΗΣΗ ΤΗΣ ΦΟΡΟΛΟΓΙΚΗΣ ΔΙΟΙΚΗΣΗΣ ΠΩΣ ΛΕΙΤΟΥΡΓΕΙ ΣΤΗΝ ΕΛΛΑΔΑ?

Περίληψη. *Το παρόν άρθρο διερευνά τη διαδικασία ψηφιοποίησης της φορολογικής διοίκησης στην Ελλάδα και περιγράφει τις βασικές αρχές και μηχανισμούς της. Ο συγγραφέας εξετάζει την εισαγωγή των σύγχρονων τεχνολογιών πληροφορικής στο σύστημα συλλογής και λογιστικής των φορολογικών δεδομένων, καθώς και την αυτοματοποίηση των διαδικασιών της φορολογικής διοίκησης. Η μελέτη της ελληνικής εμπειρίας επιτρέπει τον εντοπισμό των βασικών πλεονεκτημάτων και των προκλήσεων που αντιμετωπίζει η εφαρμογή της ψηφιοποίησης στον τομέα αυτό.*

Λέξεις-κλειδιά: *ψηφιοποίηση, φορολογική διοίκηση, Ελλάδα, τεχνολογία πληροφοριών, αυτοματοποίηση.*

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Digitalisation of tax administration is one of the key trends in the modern economy. In an effort to achieve a more efficient and transparent tax collection and accounting system, governments are increasingly turning to the use of modern information technology. In this article, we will focus on the case of Greece to explore how the digitalisation of tax administration works in this country. We will look at the main principles and mechanisms for implementing modern technology and analyse the benefits and challenges associated with this process. Through studying the Greek experience, we will be able to identify key aspects and success factors in the digitalisation of tax administration that may be useful for other countries seeking to modernise their tax system.

Tax administration plays an important role in the economic development of any country. In a digital economy, the role of tax administration becomes even more important. Currently, countries around the world are actively implementing digital technologies in tax administration. Greece was one of the first countries to implement digital tax administration programmes. In this report, we will review Greece's experience in the field of digital tax administration, identify trends, prospects and priority areas for the development of this industry.

Trends in the development of digital tax administration in Greece

The digital breakthrough and the process of digitalisation have had a great impact on tax administration in Greece. The development and implementation of digital technologies has significantly improved tax administration procedures, which have become simpler and more efficient. However, there are major trends in the development of digital tax administration in Greece:

1. Introduction of electronic declaration

In order to simplify tax administration procedures, the possibility of electronic declaration has been introduced in Greece. Taxpayers can submit their tax declaration online through a special portal of the Tax Service. To perform this action, it is necessary to have an electronic signature or to log in to one's personal account using a personal identifier. Thus, electronic declaration provides taxpayers with the opportunity to submit tax returns and pay taxes electronically, which makes the process faster and more convenient, reduces paper documents and reduces the time spent on the tax administration process.

2- Security of tax data

When processing tax information, the Greek tax authorities ensure maximum protection of users' personal data in order to prevent the leakage of their confidential information. In this regard, Greece has developed regulations designed to ensure the security of tax data. These regulations establish requirements for the security of tax information and the protection of users' personal data.

3- Tax administration for small and medium-sized businesses

SMEs play an important role in the Greek economy. To support this sector, a tax administration has been developed that allows small businesses to submit their declarations online. Entrepreneurs can receive information about their tax obligations, fill in their declarations and pay taxes through a special portal on the website of the Hellenic Tax Authority. The state has also established a tax support and advice programme for taxpayers, which helps them to understand the intricacies of the tax system and reduce potential financial risks.

4- Intensive use of technology

As part of the strategy to develop the digital economy in Greece, the government is actively promoting the use of new technologies in tax administration. In particular, the country has already implemented a programme to introduce e-reporting and e-declaration, which aims to facilitate tax administration procedures and increase transparency in administration. Another important step in the development of digital tax administration in Greece is the use of new data analysis technologies. Based on the analysis of income and expenditure data for additional tax expenditure from unreliable taxpayers, an additional case can be initiated.

The digital economy is transforming all aspects of life, including economic activity. For those in business, the introduction of digital technology and the internet has provided new opportunities to attract customers and increase sales. However, new opportunities for tax evasion have also been created. In this regard, the digital economy has become of growing interest to tax inspectorates [1]. There was a need to adapt tax administration to the digital economy in order to compensate for the loss of revenue that occurred as a result of new tax schemes. Moreover, digital technologies have also led to the emergence of new tools in the tax field. For example, the introduction of electronic payments and multiple pass-through systems, as well as other electronic products and services, have become a basis for the tax inspectorate and an opportunity to collect data on tax liabilities at the control level. About 90 per cent of tax payments are made through electronic payment systems. With the help of electronic payment systems it is possible not only to pay taxes online, but also to fill in various declarations with electronic signature [2]. This simplifies the tax payment procedure from the point of view of companies, which can change the distribution of balance sheets and make more accessible and understandable to the public. Greece has a successful policy to provide an environment for businesses and users. Currently, Greece has been promoting a strategy to identify improper taxpayers for several years. Since the end of 2017, the "KEA" system has been in operation, which

has enabled the fiscal authorities to find tax irregularities. With the help of this system, tax officials can monitor the activities of taxpayers on the Internet (e.g. on classified websites, social networks, etc.).

Companies registered in Greece are required to submit returns through a special portal on the website of the Hellenic Tax Authority (www.aade.gr). The use of this portal is mandatory for companies of all sizes, from large multinational corporations to small and medium-sized enterprises.

According to the Hellenic Statistical Authority (Hellenic National Statistical Institute), retail accounted for 9% of the total e-commerce turnover in 2021. In some product categories, such as communication equipment or consumer electronics, e-commerce accounted for around 20%. At the same time, according to the Hellenic Federation of Tax Agencies (ΕΑΔΑ), the number of software tools used by tax authorities reached 60 thousand in 2021.

Electronic declaration

In order to simplify the declaration procedure, the possibility of electronic declaration was introduced. A taxpayer has the opportunity to submit a tax return online through a special portal of the tax service [3]. These actions can be performed by a user who has provided an electronic signature or logged into his personal account using a personal identifier.

Ensuring the security of tax data

When processing tax information, tax authorities must ensure maximum protection of users' personal data in order to prevent the leakage of their confidential information. In this regard, Greece has developed regulations designed to ensure the security of tax data during electronic processing. These regulations established requirements for the security of tax information and the protection of users' personal data.

Tax administration for SMEs

SMEs play an important role in the Greek economy. To support this sector, a tax administration has been developed that allows small businesses to submit returns online [4]. Entrepreneurs can receive information about their tax obligations, fill out declarations and pay taxes through a special portal on the website of the Greek Tax Authority.

However, many SMEs are not able to deal with tax issues themselves. In this regard, the state has created a programme of support and advice on tax issues [5]. Free tax counselling service is available to all taxpayers and helps them to understand the intricacies of the tax system and reduce possible financial risks.

Intensive use of technology

As part of the strategy to develop the digital economy in Greece, the government is actively promoting the use of new technologies in tax administration. In particular, the country has already implemented a programme to introduce e-reporting and e-declaration, which aims to facilitate tax administration procedures and increase transparency in administration.

Another important step in the development of digital tax administration in Greece is the use of new data analysis technologies. Based on the analysis of income and expenditure data for additional tax expenditure, an additional case can be opened with unreliable taxpayers.

Conclusion and recommendations

In conclusion, it can be said that Greece is at the forefront in its efforts to develop digital tax administration. Through the use of electronic technologies and the development of online services, Greece is creating the conditions for simplifying tax procedures and increasing transparency in the management of tax data. In recent years, Greece has taken a big step towards a more efficient tax administration, developing many programmes and tools that improve tax data collection and processing processes and reduce the likelihood of tax crimes.

Digital tax administration in Greece also maximises the security and confidentiality of tax data, protecting taxpayers' rights and preventing fraud. This creates the conditions for a more transparent and efficient taxation system, which contributes to the development of the economy and strengthens the country's financial stability.

Although Greece's digital tax administration is one of the most developed in Europe, there is still room for improvement. In the future, Greece can continue to develop new technologies and programmes that will further increase the efficiency of tax administration and increase flexibility in its functioning to best meet the needs of today's economy and society.

Reference:

1. Komninos, D., Dermatis, Z., Anastasiou, A., & Liargovas, P. (2020). Training needs of officials of the greek-cypriot tax administration. *Journal of Economics and Business*, 23(1).
2. Liargovas, P., Anastasiou, A., Komninos, D., & Dermatis, Z. (2019). The contribution of electronic tax transactions to increasing the productivity of Greek Tax Administration and serving services for citizens and businesses. *China-USA Business Review*, 18(1), 12-21.
3. Γεωργίου, Σ. (2023). Η εξέλιξη της φοροδιαφυγής στην Ελλάδα και η συμβολή των ηλεκτρονικών βιβλίων στην καταπολέμησή της.
4. Γιαννέλη, Κ. (2022). Η Δημόσια Διοίκηση στην Ελλάδα και η μετάβαση στην ψηφιακή εποχή.

5. Κασιούλη, Μ. (2020). Πολυπλοκότητα του φορολογικού συστήματος: λόγοι, αίτια και αντιμετώπιση.
6. Λεονταρίδη, Ε. (2023). Η αντιληπτή πολυπλοκότητα του φορολογικού συστήματος: μία ανάλυση μέσα από τη χρησιμότητα των πληροφοριακών συστημάτων και η πιθανότητα απλοποίησης φορολογικών διαδικασιών.
7. Παπανικολάου, Χ. (2023). Ο ψηφιακός μετασχηματισμός των φορολογικών διοικήσεων-Η ελληνική προοπτική.
8. Τραυλού, Β. (2017). Φορολογική Διοίκηση και Ηλεκτρονική Διακυβέρνηση: Συγκριτική Μελέτη Ελλάδας-Σουηδίας.

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Жўраева, Н.Қ. Уй-жой коммунал соҳаси фаолиятини бошқариш механизмларини такомиллаштириш. Монография. - Фарғона: Al-Ferganus, 2021.- 140 б.

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Mirzaev, A.T. Methodological aspects of tourism and recreational activity management in Uzbekistan: changes and prospects: Monograph /Mirzaev A.T.; ed G. Sh. Khankeldiyeva - Fergana: Al-Ferganus, 2021.- 174 p.

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Муминова, Е.А.
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Монография

Фарғона - AL - FERGANUS - 2021

Nazarmatov, O.S.

Improving the methodology of management of innovative processes in the enterprises of the textile industry. Monograph. - Fergana: Al-Ferganus, 2021.- 200 p.

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UBAYDULLAYEV M.M.

G'O'ZADA DEFOLIATSIYA O'TKAZISHNING
MAQBUL ME'YOR VA MUDDATLARI

Monografiya

Farg'ona - AL - FERGANUS - 2021

Ubaydullayev M.M.

G'o'zada defoliatsiya o'tkazishning maqbul me'yor va muddatlari. Monografiya. /q.x.f.d., professor F.J. Teshayev muharrirligi ostida. Farg'ona: Al-Ferganus, 2021. – 160 b.

ISBN: 978-9943-7706-6-9

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